

**Synthesis and Fungicidal Activity of some
New Bis-heterocycles**

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THIOSEMICARBAZIDES are associated with diverse biocidal¹ activities probably by virtue of a toxophoric N-C=S group. Various substituted thiazoles² and triazoles³ are known to exhibit signi-

ficant biological activities. Similarly, a comparative study of mercapto compounds and their sulphides has revealed that the sulphides are relatively more active⁴ than the parent mercapto compounds. Several heterocyclic sulphides have been reported to display antitubercular⁴ and antifungal⁵ activities. These observations stimulated us to synthesise the title compounds with a view to screen their fungicidal activity.

4,4'-Diarylbis-oxalyl/malonyl/succinyl/adipylthiosemicarbazides (**2a-j**) were prepared by refluxing a mixture of acid hydrazides and aryl isothiocyanates in methanol which on acidic cyclisation furnished bis(5-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)alkanes (**3a-j**). On treatment with NaOH (8%), the thiosemicarbazides yielded bis(4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl)alkanes (**4a-j**) which were then condensed with alkyl halides to afford bis-alkyl(4-aryl-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl-ethane-5-yl)sulphides (**5a-1**) (Scheme 1). All

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	M p. °C	Yield %
2a	160	80
2b	80	88
2c	158	81
2d	56	75
2e	160	81
2f	182	78
2g	173	76
2h	162	75
2i	185	82
2j	150	79
3a	100	77
3b	180	85
3c	156	86
3d	185	80
3e	120	78
3f	180	74
3g	81	78
3h	85	84
3i	96	77
3j	76	61
4a	115	63
4b	300	74
4c	225	75
4d	200	64
4e	300	78
4f	300	77
4g	> 300	63
4h	245	80
4i	185	77
4j	160	71
5a	220	72
5b	200	71
5c	152	71
5d	98	70
5e	180	79
5f	196	77
5g	Semi-solid	78
5h	58	74
5i	200	70
5j	205	76
5k	31	65
5l	55	69

*All compounds showed satisfactory N and S analyses.

2, 3 and 4

(n); R = **a** (0); 2,3-Me₂
b (1); 2-Me
c (1); 2-OEt
d (1); 2,3-Me₂
e (2); H
f (2); 2-Me
g (2); 4-Me
h (2); 2-OEt
i (4); 2,3-Me₂
j (4); 3,4-Cl₂

5 (n=2)

R; R¹ = **a** H; Me
b H; Et
c H; n-Pr
d H; n-Bu
e 2-Me; Me
f 2-Me; Et
g 2-Me; n-Pr
h 2-Me; n-Bu
i 4-Me; Me
j 4-Me; Et
k 4-Me; n-Pr
l 4-Me; n-Bu

Scheme 1

the compounds (Table 1) were characterised by the elemental analyses and spectral data. Compounds **3a** and **4a** are not bis-alkanes but have been described under the bis-alkane series for obvious reason.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer at 90 MHz using TMS as internal reference. Procedure for one typical case of each step has been described. The acid hydrazides were prepared by known method.

4,4'-Diarylbis-oxalyl/malonyl/succinyl/adipylthiosemicarbazides (**2a-j**)⁶: A methanolic solution of the acid hydrazide (1; 0.01 mol) and aryl isothiocyanate (0.022 mol) was refluxed for 4 h and then cooled. The resulting solid was washed and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol to yield **2a** as white crystals (80%), m.p. 160° (Found: N, 18.82; S, 14.50. C₂₀H₂₄N₆O₂S₂ requires: N, 18.92; S, 14.41%); ν_{max} 3 400 (NH), 1 660 (C=O), 1 380 (C-CH₂) and 1 120 cm⁻¹(C=S); δ (DMSO-d₆) 2.4,

NOTES

2.6 (12H, s, each 2(2×CH₃)), 6.6–7.2 (6H, m, ArH) and 9.4–9.8 (6H, b, NH).

Bis(5-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)alkanes⁵ (3a–j): The thiosemicarbazide (2; 0.005 mol) was dissolved in ice-cold concentrated sulphuric acid (10 ml) and the solution was kept at room temperature for 2 h, stirred occasionally and then poured over crushed ice. The resulting solid was washed with water and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol as a white solid (3e; 78%), m.p. 120° (Found: N, 22.03; S, 16.76. C₁₈H₁₆N₆S₂ requires: N, 22.10; S, 16.84%); ν_{\max} 3 300 (NH), 1 540 (C=N) and 700 cm⁻¹ (C–S–C); δ (DMSO-d₆) 2.7–3.1 (4H, m, 2×CH₂), 6.9–7.8 (10H, m, ArH) and 8.7–8.9 (2H, b, 2×NH).

Bis(4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl)alkanes⁵ (4a–j): The thiosemicarbazide (2; 0.005 mol) was refluxed with sodium hydroxide (8%, 25 ml) for 4 h and cooled. It was then poured into large excess of cold water, stirred and filtered. The filtrate on acidification with cold dilute HCl yielded a solid which was washed and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol as a white solid (4b; 74%), m.p. 300° (Found: N, 21.21; S, 16.14. C₁₉H₁₈N₆S₂ requires: N, 21.32; S, 16.24%); ν_{\max} 3 350 (NH), 2 560 (SH), 1 580 (C=N) and 1 160 cm⁻¹ (C=S); δ (DMSO-d₆) 2.2 (6H, s, 2×CH₃), 3.0 (2H, s, CH₂) and 6.7–7.4 (10H, m, ArH).

Bisalkyl(4-aryl-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl-ethane-5-yl)sulphides⁵ (5a–l): A mixture of methanolic solution of bistriazolyl ethane (4e–g; 0.005 mol), alkyl halide (0.01 mol) and fused sodium acetate (2.0 g) was refluxed gently for 4 h, cooled and then poured into water. The resulting solid was washed and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol to give 5i (70%), m.p. 200° (Found: N, 19.39; S, 14.48. C₂₂H₂₄N₆S₂ requires: N, 19.27; S, 14.68%); ν_{\max} 1 580 (C=N) and 1 420 cm⁻¹ (S–CH₃); δ (DMSO-d₆) 2.1 (6H, s, 2×CH₃–S), 2.4 (6H, s, 2×CH₃–Ar), 2.7–3.1 (4H, m, 2×CH₂) and 7.2–7.65 (8H, m, ArH).

Fungicidal screening: All the compounds were screened for their fungicidal activity⁵ against *A. flavus*, *H. oryzae* and *C. sacchari* at three different concentrations, viz. 1000, 100 and 10 ppm; commercial fungicide BLITOX 50 WP was used as control.

All the compounds were found to be fairly toxic against all the fungi at 1000 ppm, but their toxicity decreased markedly on dilution at 100 ppm and 10 ppm. They were, however, more toxic against *H. oryzae* than against *A. flavus* and *C. sacchari*. Compounds 3j, 4i and 4j were found to be more active than others and inhibited >40% growth of all the three fungi at 10 ppm. The activity of these compounds (around 90%) were quite comparable with the control (>95%) at 1000 ppm. In general, triazoles and thiadiazoles exhibited good activity as compared to their parent thiosemicarbazides; bisalkyl sulphides were less active than their parent triazoles. Furthermore, a slight increase in the

fungicidal activity was appeared with an increase in the number of methylene group.

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